

MENTAL HEALTH OF SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH RESPECT TO GENDER AND SELF-CONCEPT

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Abstract

The present study was carried out to study mental health of senior secondary school students with respect to gender and self-concept. In the present study, survey technique under descriptive research was used. Multistage sampling along with stratified random sampling and incidental sampling were used to select the sample of 737 senior secondary school students (314 males and 423 females) of +2 class. Standardised tool 'Mental Health Battery' by Arun Kumar Singh and Alpana Sen Gupta and self-made tool 'Self-Concept Scale' were used to collect the necessary data. Collected data was analysed by applying descriptive statistics and Analysis of Variance. The findings of the study indicated that male and female senior secondary school students possessed similar level of mental health. Senior secondary school students having different level of self-concept differed significantly with respect to their mental health. Gender and self-concept do not interact significantly with respect to mental health of senior secondary school students.

Keywords: *Mental Health, Gender, Self-Concept*

INTRODUCTION

Good health is important to live happy and prosperous life. Good health means physical and emotional well-being, better body functioning and free from disease, pain or injury. Health is most precious asset an individual has. It enables the individual to enjoy life and fulfil their goals. Mentally healthy person can work for his own development and for the development of society. A healthy individual makes a healthy society. Phrase 'Survival for fitness' has come back in the field of health. In the modern times machine has made human life less active. For healthy life, it is essential for a person to remain active. To live a healthy life a person must be

physically, mentally, socially and emotionally healthy. Mental health is the fundamental factor that make the balance between physical health and other aspects of life. Mental health is the ability of a person that help to meet the demands of life based on their abilities and limitations. It is important components of overall well-being. According to **World Health Organisation (1981)** “Mental health is the capacity of the individual, the group and the environment to interact with one another in ways that promote subjective well-being, the optimal development and use of mental abilities (cognitive, affective and relational), the achievement of individual and collective goals consistent with justice and the attainment and preservation of conditions of fundamental equality”. A person with good mental health can face challenges of life, adjust to environment and feel more confident in their abilities. This help to develop the self-concept of a person. Self-concept means knowledge about oneself. It is evaluation of ourself. Self-concept includes thought, feelings and beliefs about oneself. There are two aspects of self-concept ‘I’ and ‘ME’. I mean self-awareness. All qualities that make the self-unique consists of ‘ME’ self. For the development of personality self-concept play important role. Development of self-concept is dynamic process and acquired in social setting. Development of self-concept is life long process. Self-concept is an important aspect of development in adolescence age. Adolescence is characteristics by different physical, emotional, cognitive and social changes. It is a period of significant self-discovery. Human behaviour is determined by his self-concept. Self-concept not only affect behaviour but also affect mental health. **Zhu et al. (2016)** highlighted that mental health, self-concept and social adaptation were related significantly. Self-concept of college students was directly affecting the mental health of college students. **Singh (2018)** concluded that significant difference existed in mental health of secondary school boys and girls and no significant difference existed between mental health of rural and urban secondary school students. **Parmar (2019)** highlighted no significant difference in mental health of senior secondary school students on the basis of gender and locality. There was significant relationship in mental health and emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students. **Bahu et al. (2020)** revealed that significant difference founded in mental health of boys and girls and non-significant difference between boys and girls in their self-esteem. There was positive correlation between mental health and self-esteem. **Thapliyal (2022)** showed that no significant difference existed between mental health of male and female secondary school students. gender had no effect on mental health. There was significant correlation between mental health and academic achievement of secondary school students. **Bhargava (2022)** concluded that significant difference existed in mental health of male and

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female students. Male students showed higher self-concept scores as compare to female students. Significant difference was also found between rural and urban students. Self-concept scores of rural students were higher than the urban students. There was significant relation between self-concept and family environment. **Babu and Suneela (2024)** revealed that all adolescents students fall above average level of mental health. There was significant difference between mental health of male and female students and students belonging to nuclear and joint family. There was no significant difference in mental health of students belonging to rural and urban area.

On the basis of thorough review of the literature it has been observed that very few studies were found on mental health of students with respect to their self-concept and no specific conclusion could be made about the mental health of student in relation to gender. Hence, it was decided to study the mental health of senior secondary school students with respect to gender and self-concept.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the mental health of senior secondary school students with respect to their gender.
2. To study the difference in mental health of senior secondary school students with respect to their level of self-concept.
3. To study the interactional effect of gender and self-concept on mental health of senior secondary school students.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

1. There exists no significant difference in mental health of senior secondary school students with respect to their gender.
2. There exists no significant difference in mental health of senior secondary school students with respect to their level of self-concept.
3. There exists no significant interactional effect of gender and self-concept on mental health of senior secondary school students.

METHODOLOGY

To achieve the objectives of the study survey technique under descriptive research was used.

SAMPLING

In the present study, a representative sample of 737 senior secondary school students (314 males and 423 females) of +2 class were selected from schools of Mandi, Kullu, Hamirpur and

Bilaspur districts of Himachal Pradesh by applying multistage sampling along with the process of stratified random sampling and incidental sampling.

TOOLS USED

- ‘Mental Health Battery’ developed by Arun Kumar Singh and Alpana Sen Gupta was used.
- ‘Self-Concept Scale’ developed and standardised by investigator herself.

ANALYSIS OF DATA

Descriptive statistics and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were used to analyse the collected data. Detail of analysis is given below:

In order to study the main and interaction effect of gender and level of self-concept on mental health of senior secondary school students, Analysis of Variance (2x3 factor design) involving two types of gender i.e. male and female and three level of self-concept i.e. high, average and low, was applied on the mean scores of mental health. The mean and standard deviation of mental health scores with respect to gender and level of self-concept are given in Table-1

TABLE -1
MEAN AND STANDARD DEVIATION OF MENTAL HEALTH OF SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH RESPECT TO GENDER AND SELF-CONCEPT

Sr. No	LEVEL OF Self-Concept	Mean Mental Health Scores				
		High Level	Average Level	Low Level	Total	
GENDER						
1.	Male (314)	Mean	81.68	82.82	77.36	81.61
		S.D.	11.281	9.481	10.498	10.068
		N	28	222	64	314
2.	Female (423)	Mean	84.34	82.13	77.60	82.13
		S.D.	9.627	9.591	9.654	9.742
		N	87	293	43	423
3.	Total (737)	Mean	83.70	82.43	77.46	81.91
		S.D.	10.068	9.540	10.121	9.879
		N	115	515	107	737

From the mean scores of mental health of senior secondary school students with respect to gender and self-concept, 'F' values were calculated. The results are given in table 2

TABLE- 2
SUMMARY OF RESULTS OF ANALYSIS OF VARIANCE OF MENTAL HEALTH OF SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN RELATION TO GENDER AND SELF-CONCEPT

Sr. No	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square (Variance)	F-Ratio
1.	Gender	52.441	1	52.441	0.556 ^{NS}
2.	Self-Concept	2275.299	2	1137.649	12.055 ^{**}
3.	Gender X Self-Concept	209.008	2	104.504	1.107 ^{NS}
4.	Error Variance	68986.733	731	94.373	
4	Total sum of squares	5016105.000	737		
5	Corrected Total	71826.540	736		

NS- Not Significant

**.- Significant at 0.01 Level of Significance

(I) Main Effects

(a) Gender (A)

The obtained value of 'F' for the main effect of gender on mental health of senior secondary school students for df 1/731, came out to be 0.556, which is much less than the table value 3.85 even at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the Hypothesis No 1 "There will be no significant difference in mental health of senior secondary school students with respect to gender" was accepted. It indicates that male and female senior secondary school students possessed similar level of mental health. It indicates that male and female senior secondary school students did not differ significantly in terms of their mental health. This is also evident from the mean mental health scores of male (81.61) and female (82.13) senior secondary school students, which are almost equal.

The mean mental health scores of male and female senior secondary school students can also be shown from figure 1

Figure- 1
MEAN MENTAL HEALTH SCORES OF MALE AND FEMALE SENIOR
SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS.

(b) Self-Concept (B)

Table-2 further shows that the computed value of 'F' for the main effect of self-concept on mental health of senior secondary school students for, $df\ 2/731$ came out to be 12.055, which is greater than the table value 4.63 even at 0.01 level of significance. Hence Hypothesis No. 2 "There will be no significant difference in mental health of senior secondary school students at different levels of self-concept" was not retained. Thus, it may be interpreted that senior secondary school students having high, average and low level of self-concept differed significantly in their mental health.

Further, it is also evident from mean mental health scores of senior secondary school students with high self-concept (83.70), which is higher than the score of senior secondary school students with average self-concept (82.43) and low self-concept (77.46).

Further in order to find out the significance difference in mental health scores of senior secondary school students possessing different level of self-concept in different combinations (considering two groups at a time), Tukey-Kramer test was applied. The computed and critical values of 'q' (studentized ranges statistic) and respective mean differences are given in table-3

TABLE- 3
COMPUTED AND CRITICAL VALUE OF ‘q’ (STUDENTIZED RANGE STATISTIC)
AND RESPECTED MEAN DIFFERENCE IN MENTAL HEALTH OF SENIOR
SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH DIFFERENT LEVEL OF SELF-
CONCEPT

	Self- Concept Level	mean mental health scores	Pair of Comparison	Mean Difference	Computed value of ‘q’
A1	High	83.70	A1-A2	1.27	1.98 ^{NS}
A2	Average	82.43	A2-A3	4.97	5.04*
A3	Low	77.46	A1-A3	6.24	6.83*

NS.....Not significant

*.....Significant at 0.05 level of significance

Critical value of ‘q’= 3.31 (at 0.05 level) and 4.12 (at 0.01 level), (for df 731, Numbers of groups compared=3)

The computed value of ‘q’ (Studentized Range Statistic) for mental health scores were compared with the critical value (Table value of ‘q’) for three groups of senior secondary school students classified on the basis of their level of self-concept. It was revealed that senior secondary school students possessing high and average level of self-concept had reflected significantly high level of mental health as compared to the senior secondary school student with low level of self-concept because the respective computed ‘q’ values i.e. 5.04 (Average Vs. Low) and 6.83 (High Vs. Low) were significantly higher than the critical value of ‘q’ (3.31) at 0.05 level of significance, df 2/731. So, it may be averred that senior secondary school students with low level of self-concept had shown significantly low level of mental health as compared to students possessing either high or average level of self-concept. On the other hand, the senior secondary school students with high level of self-concept did not differ significantly in terms of mental health from the students possessing average level of self-concept because the computed ‘q’ value (1.98) fall short of the critical ‘q’ value (3.33) even at 0.05 level of significance.

(II) Interactional Effect (AXB)

The calculated value of ‘F’ for the interactional effect of gender and self-concept on mental health of senior secondary school students, for degree of freedom 2 and 737 came out to 1.107. This value is below the table value of ‘F’ i.e. 3.00 at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that

Hypothesis No 3 “Gender and self-concept will not interact significantly with regard to mental health of senior secondary school students” was retained. It means that there was no significant interaction effect between gender and self-concept with respect to mental health of senior secondary school students. Therefore, it may be interpreted that the gender and self-concept taken together did not significantly affected mental health of senior secondary school students.

CONCLUSION

1. Male and female senior secondary school students possessed similar level of mental health. However, mean mental health scores of female senior secondary school students (82.13) was higher than male senior secondary school students (81.61).
2. Senior secondary school students having different level of self-concept differed from each other in their mental health. Senior secondary school students possessing high and average level of self-concept had reflected significantly high level of mental health as compared to the senior secondary school student with low level of self-concept. Senior secondary school students with high level of self-concept did not differ significantly in terms of mental health from the students possessing average level of self-concept.
3. Gender and self-concept do not interact significantly with respect to mental health of senior secondary school students. Therefore, it may be interpreted that the gender and self-concept taken together did not significantly affected mental health of senior secondary school students.

IMPLICATIONS

The present study was undertaken to study the mental health of senior secondary school students with respect to gender and self-concept. After finding the conclusion it was revealed that there was no significant gender difference in mental health of male and female senior secondary school students. However, mean mental health scores of female senior secondary school students (82.13) was higher than male senior secondary school students (81.61). Parents and teachers should focus on common students challenges rather than dividing the students on the basis of gender. They should provide the conducive environment, understanding children needs, provide emotional support and help to set realistic goals. All these factors positively affect the mental health of children. The present study also showed that senior secondary school students having different level of self-concept differed from each other in their mental health. Healthy self-image should be promoted and make students responsible for their own action. Children should be encouraged to take part in different activities. When children take part in

different activities it develops different skill among children and enhance their self-concept. The cooperation of teachers and parents is essential for development of self-concept.

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